

How does quality experience affect customer's repeat purchase? Evidence from a call center in the Philippines

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Customer satisfaction management is expected to sustain firms and call centers by keeping customers. Adapting measures from the SERVQUAL model, the purpose of this research was to determine the factors contributing to the quality of customers' experience with phone support, and their subsequent impact on the repeat purchase of products. Using Ordinal Logistic Regression method, we analyzed respondents representing American customers encountered through Filipino technical support agents in a call center in the Philippines. With ranked ratings, findings indicate that wait time, communication, attitude, product, first call resolution (one call) have significant impacts on the overall customers' experience with the phone support. The quality of overall customers' experience has significant impacts on the likelihood of repeat purchase. Other factors relating to quality customers' experience and repeat purchase among call center customers of other products and services can be investigated to strengthen knowledge and strategy for a sustainable call center customer base.

Keywords: call center, customer satisfaction, repeat purchase

Received Dec 12, 2020, Revised Feb 28, 2021 & May 16, 2021; Accepted June 2, 2021

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5044552>

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Introduction

Customer experience became a relevant topic of discussion in the corporate world (Batra 2018). Customer services through websites, chats, and emails are widely accepted nowadays, but phone support remains to be preferred by many customers because of the intimacy in communication (Jewitt & Macley 2019). This empirical study validates the impact of the antecedents identified by SERVQUAL model on customer experience and repeat purchase of products (Li & Tsung 2013, Parasuraman et al. 1985). These factors are: the effects of wait time, communication, resolution, attitude, product, and first call resolution (FCR). Satisfied customers help sustain the call centers. The individual customers of call centers—as the units of analysis—measure customer satisfaction and provide feedback to continuously improve products and services. “Customer satisfaction is the complete fulfillment of one’s expectations and an attitude or feeling that results from use of products and services” (Oliver 1980). It was found that contact service excellence had limited literature (Bueno, Weber, Bomfim & Kato 2019, Dharamdass & Fernando 2018). The

determinants of excellence were people, hiring criteria for call center agents, training and development, rewards system, team structure and cross-functional coordination systems (Dharamdass & Fernando 2018).

In the review of related literature, there appears to be insufficient empirical observations about the factors that affect customers' experience and repeat purchase in the call center industry (Bueno et al. 2019). There were limitations on the number of studies, cases, and generalizability to validate the factors that satisfy the customers of call centers (Dharamdass & Fernando 2018). Further, there was insufficient attention to value capture and long-term socio-economic transformation, especially in the Philippines call centers (Kleibert & Mann 2020). Call center companies needed to be systematic and excel by continuously satisfying their customers through engaged employees, although, are not easy because call center agents were prone to mental and emotional exhaustion (Charoensukmongkol & Puyod 2020, Santos 2020).

A contextual limitation was the measurement of the impacts to customers if there was no interaction with service providers at all. There were also limited research topics studied about call centers. Govender and Essop (2016) studied the impact of outsourcing, a comprehensive financial comparison between outsourcing and an in-house call center, and the outcome of facilities on call center operations. However, Chicu, Ryan and Valverde-Aparicio (2016) viewed that the study of customer satisfaction in call centers did not receive much academic attention unlike the study of customer satisfaction in customer relationships that required personal communication.

Philippines is an ideal emerging market to conduct our investigations as it has more US-based clients (Hechanova, 2013, Macaraig 2010). Philippines also ranks as 2nd highest for communication and 5th best country for call center reliability (Lu, Thelen & Gregory 2020). As one of the biggest industries in the country, the Philippine call center continues to grow because of availability of great number of computer-literate and English-speaking talents and employees and generates more than \$5.5b as one of the call center capitals in the world. Customer satisfaction with the call centers and the timely responses to requests, inquiries, or complaints are some of the focused areas that are taken care of by phone support firms to gain advantage over competition (Rendon et al. 2017). Manaka and Thangadurai (2017) argue that customer relation management is vital to business development through reinforcement of profitable environment and the improvements of products and services with deep customer knowledge of customer opinions. An emphasis on customer service to prevents customers from switching to alternative products and services (Oodith & Parumasur 2015). Current roles of firm's call center include customer management by call center agents for customer interaction and loyalty through ease, quality and speed of communication, and access to ensure great customers' experience and performance effectiveness of a call center. Baraykar, Tatoglu, Turkyilmaz, Delen and Zaim (2012) emphasize the concept of customer satisfaction and loyalty. The higher customer satisfaction and loyalty lead to stronger competitive position that contributes to greater market share and profitability (Baraykar et al. 2012).

The purpose of our study is to address, how does quality experience affect customer's repeat purchase in phone support? Specifically, we aim to answer: What are the significant predictors of the overall quality of phone support customers' experience? What are the impacts of the overall quality of phone support customers' experience on the likelihood of repeat purchase?

In the following sections we present our conceptual framework, develop hypotheses, present findings and discuss their relevance for marketing managers in the context of call center.

Conceptual Framework and Hypotheses Development

Most of the reviewed literature about customer satisfaction in call centers lacked number of cases and struggled to generalize the results. Govender and Essop (2016) considered the study of only one company as a limitation to generalize research outcome with other companies. Muswera, Jordaan and Matikiti (2014) implied that there was a need to establish quantitative and longitudinal research results about

customer satisfaction in call centers that satisfied random sampling method on respondents and data gathering. Chicu et al. (2016) delivered a theoretical contribution instead of empirical research on customer satisfaction phenomena in remote service and found out that human service quality leads to customer satisfaction. Muswera, Jordaan and Matikiti (2014) considered the measurement of perceived service quality in terms of expectations and customer perceptions at the same period as a limitation of their research on respondents' perceptions of call center service quality.

To understand the call center operations, both customer and agent behavior must be given full consideration about their roles in the service system (Ellway 2016). The SERVQUAL model (Parasuraman et al. 1985) and the framework of Jaiswal (2008) pointed out that resolution of concerns, wait time, communication, attitude, product quality, first call resolution (FCR) and length of time to resolve concerns have significant impacts on the overall satisfaction of the customers on the quality of their experience. Experiences of customer satisfaction and quality experience led to repeat purchase, customer loyalty and sustainable business (Aburayya et al. 2020). Figure 1 presents graphical representations of the hypotheses that we intend to test empirically.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Source: Lao & Pasco (2018); Adopted from Parasuraman et al. (1985)

Resolution and Quality of Customer Experience

When it comes to resolution and customers' experience, few comments were received from several research and indicated the weak curiosity in this factor (Markoulidakis, Rallis, Georgoulas, Kopsiaftis, Doulamis & Doulamis 2020). Bhale and Bedi (2021) cited Soderlund & Rosengreen (2008) that politeness, empathy on customers and resolution of customer complaints may lead to customer satisfaction or quality customers' experience. Mehrotra, Ross, Ryder & Zhou (2012) measured overall call center performance and customers' experience with resolution rate that involved no follow up by customers. With the speed and clarity in communication with customers, the extent to which call centers integrated CRM technology to its strategic business units might be highlighted by success from call resolution before expecting any positive impact on caller satisfactions (Abdullateef et al. 2011). The results somewhat contradict the model of Jaiswal (2008). So we test our first hypothesis:

H1. Resolution has significant impact on the overall rating of customers on the quality of their experience with phone support.

Wait Time and Quality of Customer Experience

Wait times were valuable when related to quality products and services (Giebelhausen et al. 2011). Giebelhausen, Robinson, and Cronin (2011, p 898) implied that “when marketers strive to eliminate waiting time, they might not only forgo an opportunity to increase consumer satisfaction, but they might be actively suppressing it.” Kumar (2012) argued that wait times in a call center are typically large, and the call center is not open 24/7. However, customers can find precise answers to their queries from the CSRs. As moderated by characteristics of web portal, the usage of web portals increased if the information involved were unambiguous. Garcia, Archer, Moradi and Ghiabi (2012) concluded that although there are waiting times, informative satisfactory answers and top of the line service keep customers satisfaction and positive experience. Low wage segments were more sensitive to waiting time than high wage segments (Xia, Chen, Jayaraman & Munson 2015). Understanding customer patience behavior is essential in call center management with changes in wait time sensitivity based on different service disciplines and types (Aksin, Ata, Emadi & Su 2013). Our proposed second hypothesis is:

H2. Wait time has significant impact on the overall rating of customers on the quality of their experience with phone support.

Communication and Quality of Customer Experience

Communication is the key to adoption of new technology to ensure adoption of self-service more readily (Oodith 2019). Rendon, Vasquez, Benjumes-Arias & Valencia-Arias (2017, p 15) concluded that “the service in the call centers and timely response to requests, inquiries, or complaints, and an effective service were among the factors that mostly influenced the satisfaction of users of telecommunications services.” Abdullateef et al. (2011) also investigated that technology-based customer relations management (CRM) influenced perceived service quality. According to Agarwal, Singh and Thakur (2013), call center itself is a major communication channel for customers. Emphatic communication can help mitigate tensions in customer calls but objective communication, genuine emotional support, affective and cognitive empathy in communication can influence call resolutions and customer experiences (Clark, Murfett, Rogers & Ang 2013). In contrast, Saberi, Hussain and Chang (2015) argued that firms utilized call centers to enhance the communication to customers and found that lack of data integrity was an important issue to be managed by call centers. But Agyapong (2011) concluded that the dimensions of SERVQUAL model such as competence, courtesy, tangibility, reliability, responsiveness and communication affect customer satisfaction in telecommunications industry. Park, Chung, Gunn and Rutherford (2015) found that effective communication and e-listening was highly related to interpersonal service quality and utilitarian value. Moreover, Lew, Walther. Pang and Shin (2018) then incorporated aspects of interactivity in communication to the social information processing (SIP) theory of computer-mediated communication that addressed the conversational behaviors that influence interpersonal relations. We present our third hypothesis.

H3. Communication has significant impact on the overall rating of customers on the quality of their experience with phone support.

Attitude and Quality of Customer Experience

Chicu et al. (2016) gave importance to positive human resources practices to increase the performance of call center employees in terms of burnt-out, absenteeism, and attrition. It became the task of the firm's call center to cradle customer interaction, attitude, and loyalty through ease and speed of access, quality

and ease of communication with call center agents (Oodith & Parumasur 2015). Attitude was important to look at in developing quality customer experience. Rafaeli, Ziklik and Doucet (2008) cited Loveock (2001) and Tansik & Smith (2000) that scripts were utilized to overcome the differences in attitudes and kept quality interactions between employees and customers. However, Agarwal et al. (2013) argued that tangibility and empathy have weak impacts on service quality and customer satisfaction. Akesson, Edvardsson and Trobvoll (2014) identified favorable and unfavorable customer experience drivers that guide value co-creation and explain how the flow of value co-creation helps form customers' experiences. The experience drivers were grounded in norms and rules within the specific context in which actors create meaning through communication activities. Further, convenience, credibility, employees' competence and compassion, and service context are factors on customer experience (Wasan 2018). Furthermore, Alcover, Chambel and Estreder (2020) showed that the level of performance-contingent rewards (team-level) guided the team's autonomous motivation (team-level) and fostered employees' affective commitment (individual-level). Labach (2010) concluded that the attitude of customer service representatives were vital to overall customer experience. Our fourth hypothesis is as follow:

H4. Attitude has significant impact on the overall rating of customers on the quality of their experience with phone support.

Product and Quality of Customer Experience

Bueno, Weber, Bomfin and Kato (2019, p 15) confirmed that products and services are related to customer experience and categorized dimensions such as "predispositions, interactions, and reactions." Also, services delivery affect customer experience (Bhale & Bedi 2021). Agarwal et al. (2013) noted that responsiveness and reliability affect customer satisfaction. Van Dan, Blemer and Henseler (2011) argued that product information and the suitability of products to customer's situation influences quality customer experience. In support, Sheth, Jain and Ambika (2020) reiterated that product is a fundamental marketing mix that affect customer experience. It seemed that the role of post-sales customer support such as delivery, installation, maintenance, financing, response to complaints and other questions that customers have after the purchase, while using the product were absent in the market because markets focus on the buyer and not the user (Sheth et al. 2020). Simply, Alfa, Addae, Inkumsah and Amponsah (2021) found that there was an association between satisfaction and loyalty behavior although better customer satisfaction was not an enough basis for consumers' loyalty. As customer satisfaction measured the ways companies supply products and services, customer satisfaction also assessed the product use experience compared to the buyer's value expectations (Razak & Shamsudin 2019). Customer experience was commonly measured based on quality of products and services. Maklan and Klaus (2011) recommended to maximize the drivers of financial performance, like loyalty, satisfaction and share-of-wallet. We present our fifth hypothesis:

H5. Product has significant impact on the overall rating of customers on the quality of their experience with phone support.

First Call Resolution and Quality of Customer Experience

Govender and Essop (2016) defined customer experience as the personal interpretation of the service and quality provided by the firm wherein the knowledge of agents, friendliness, and first call resolution (FCR) that affected customer experience in call centers. FCR were proven to be statistically related to repurchase, but insistence and repeated calls were removed since no significant relationship was found (Fernandes, 2013). Batra (2018) also argued that first contact resolution (FCR) and succeeding contacts affect customer experience and that a poorly handled FCR can stop a supplier-customer relationship. Clearly, Sultana (2008) recognized the importance of quality customers' experiences from the effectiveness and efficiency

of call centers as determined by first call resolution rates. Labach (2010) cited Levin (2007) that there was one percent improvement in customer satisfaction for every one percent improvement in first call resolution. Our sixth hypothesis to be tested is as follow:

H6. First call resolution has significant impact on the overall rating of customers on the quality of their experience with phone support.

Quality of Customer Experience and Repeat Purchase

Park (2020) ranked the evaluation factors for service quality as interaction quality tagged as the most important, followed by outcome quality and physical environment quality. Such study was a guideline for establishing a standard for the service quality of customer center in practice (Park 2020). The high level of customer orientation positively influenced quality of service and eventually resulted in consumer loyalty and satisfaction (Aburayya, Marzouqi, Alawadhi, Abdouli & Taryam 2020). Park, Chung, Gunn and Rutherford (2015, p 49) concluded that "e-listening was related to interpersonal service quality and utilitarian value, while the interpersonal service quality was directly related to e-satisfaction and e-loyalty in e-contact centers." Lestari and Ellyawati (2019) proved that online service quality (ease of use, website design, security assurance, responsiveness, and personalization) affected repurchase intention and satisfaction. Sarrab, Elbasir and Alnaeli (2016, p 100) described a model of "mobile learning service quality, including availability, fast response times, flexibility, scalability, usability, maintainability, functionality, functionality, reliability, connectivity, performance, user interface and security that are dependent on learner satisfaction." Customers' experience was determinant in future purchase behavior considering both positive and negative experiences were the main antecedents of mobile phone renewal, upgrading or switching behaviors (Alshurideh, Nicholson & Xiao 2012). Any company increased the customer experience by improvement of consumer service delivery (Bhale & Bedi 2021). As cited in Lemon and Verhoef (2016, p 78), "customers develop relationships with brands (Fournier 1998), which influence their identity (Bhattacharya & Sen 2003), customer decisions become routinized (Sheth & Parvatiyar 1995), and extraordinary experiences have long-lasting effects (Arnould and Price 1993)." In the case of Airbnb customer experience home benefits, personalized services, authenticity, and social connections significantly affect customers' behavioral intentions such as repeat purchase and customer loyalty (Li, Hudson & So 2019). Customer experience was important in loyalty programs, because a positive experience regarding the benefits that loyalty programs offer influence the customers' acceptance, interaction, purchasing and higher repeat purchase (Alshurideh et al. 2012, Verhoef et al. 2009). A strong customer orientation influences positive customer evaluations as compared to the differences in the locations of call centers (Walsh, Gouthier, Gremler & Brach 2012). Our final hypothesis is:

H7. Quality customers' experience has significant impact on the likelihood of repeat purchase

Methodology

This study was a quantitative, causal, and cross-sectional research. The ordinal data were determinants in the choice of non-parametric statistical tests- ordinal regression that had no assumptions tested (Hair, Black, Babin & Anderson 2010). This cross-sectional study followed a survey type of research method. Ordinal logistic regression was used to build models, generate predictions, and to evaluate the importance of various predictor variables in cases where the dependent was ordinal in nature (Hair et al. 2010).

The researchers analyzed selected American customers from SME firms under phone support encountered through Filipino technical support agents in a call center. The respondents are the customers of one of the global leaders in providing networking products, routers and cameras and these include products and services catered by a call center based in the Philippines. There are at least 25,000 daily callers from USA and Canada to phone support concerning connection issues, inquiries on product features, first-time set-up, refunds as well as products and services complaints. The 5,803 customers have complete responses on the survey questions, within the period of 2010 to 2016. Majority of respondents use the network products and routers for personal use, or as affiliate of large enterprise and SMEs. The knowledge, smaller scales, limited capital, lack of expertise, and fewer workforce, in documentation, logistics, communication, and maintenance of information technologies made SMEs to be receptive to external support (Patmore & Haddoud 2015).

The SERVQUAL model (Parasuraman et al. 1985) was the theoretical foundation of this research. The model mostly focused on the customers' perspective that defined service quality in the aspects of reliability, assurance, tangibles, empathy, and responsiveness. In a common call center, customers could rate their experience, on a scale of 1 to 5, in areas that included first call resolution (FCR), attitude of the customer service representative, the speed of the response and other related parameters (Li & Tsung 2013). The SERVQUAL model evaluated characteristics of personnel behavior and the importance of its customer orientation as a key component of service quality (Valeeva et al. 2020).

The questions used in the study came from a 25 item-questionnaire and were deployed in the regular survey of the company. The questionnaires were adapted from the dimensions of SERVQUAL model (Parasuraman et al. 1985). The dependent variables of this research were the overall rating of customers to the quality of their experience with Phone Support (overall) and the likelihood that a customer repeats his/her purchase of the product (repeat).

Analyses and Results

Our model gave significant improvement over the baseline intercept-only model. Wait time, communication, attitude, product, and first call resolution (FCR) significantly impacts on the overall quality customers' experience and have good model fitting as measured by $-2 \log$ likelihood (1736, $p < .05$) and chi-square (4577, $p < .05$). Wait, product, communication, FCR and attitude moderately explained the overall customer experience with pseudo r^2 values with Cox and Snell (.409) and Nagelkerke (.47). Quality customers' experience impact on repeat purchase have moderate strength explanatory power with pseudo r^2 values with Cox and Snell=.63 and Nagelkerke=.74 (Hair et al. 2010).

The phone support company investigated in this research was doing a great job in measurement of overall customer experience because majority of the customers rated positively their satisfaction and relationship. About 57.1 percent out of the 5,803 customers, gave a rating of excellent; about 24 percent mentioned that the experience was very good; and, approximately 7 percent rated the experience good. Considering only those customers who responded (5,706), those three positive answers account for 88.8 percent. The ordinal regression coefficient denotes the impact on quality customers' experience for every 1.00 improvements in each specific factor (Hair et al. 2010). The frequency distribution of overall customers' experience had higher categories (4=Very Good, 5=Excellent) and higher percentages, hence more probable. The coefficients, Pearson's chi-square test, and p-values were listed, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Ordinal Regression Coefficients and Chi-Square Values with Overall Customer Experience

Variables	Estimate	Wald, p-value	number of valid cases	χ^2	p-value
Resolution	-.45	.70	5634	2159.64	.00
Wait Time	1.01	.00	5416	2349.28	.00
Communication	1.00	.00	5453	5163.65	.00
Attitude	1.09	.00	5446	4771.88	.00
Product	2.81	.00	5302	4231.80	.00
First Call Resolution	-.64	.00	5674	846.59	.00
Quality of Overall Customer Experience--> Repeat Purchase	.72	.00	5803	1014.38	.00

Notes:

Resolution: 0- No, 1-Yes

Quality of Overall Customer Experience: Wait Time, Communication, Attitude, and Product: 5-Excellent, 4-Very Good, 3-Good, 2-Fair, 3-Poor

First Call Resolution: 1-One Call, 2-Two Calls, 3-Three Calls, 4-Four Calls

Discussion

There is an indication of dependence between *resolution* and *quality of customers' experience* with phone support ($\chi^2=2159.64$, $p=.00$). But the ordinal regression coefficient was not significant (Wald test=-.46, $p=.70$), as seen in Table 1. Several research showed weak interest on the influence of resolution and customers' experience (Markoulidakis et al. 2020). Even Bhale & Bedi (2021) cited Soderlund & Rosengreen (2008) that resolution of customer complaints "might" lead to quality customers' experience. Mehrotra et al. (2012) measured was right in noting that resolution with no follow up by customers might be prerequisites. Abdullateef et al. (2011) might only indicated that call resolution was important before expecting any positive impact on caller satisfactions.

Wait time has significant impact on the quality of customers' experience with phone support (Wald test=1.01, $p=.00$; $\chi^2=2349.28$, $p=.00$). Giebelhausen et al. (2011) have similar contentions in giving stronger importance to the impacts of wait time on customer experience. Rendon, Vasquez, Benjumes-Arias & Valencia-Arias (2017, p 15) is similar in its conclusion that "the service in the call centers and timely response to requests, inquiries, or complaints, and an effective service were among the factors that mostly influenced the satisfaction of users of telecommunications services." Also, wait times were valuable when related to quality products and services (Giebelhausen et al. 2011). The results are also aligned with the findings of Giebelhausen et al. (2011), and Kumar (2012). Garcia et al. (2012) emphasized satisfactory information while Xia et al. (2015) identified low wage segments and Aksin et al. (2013) identified customer patience behavior as other related factors to consider.

Communication has significant impact on the quality of customers' experience with phone support (Wald test=1, $p=.00$; $\chi^2=5163.65$, $p=.00$). The results are supported by the research of Oodith (2019), Rendon et al. (2017), Park et al. (2015), Agarwal et al. (2013) and Abdullateef et al. (2011) although different instruments and media in communication were involved in satisfying customers with quality experience. The result of this research was also explained by the impact of interactivity (Lew et al. 2018), emphatic communication (Clark et al. 2013), and by the SERVQUAL Model (Agyapong 2011).

Attitude has significant impact on the quality of customers' experience with phone support (Wald test=1, $p=.00$; $\chi^2=4771.88$, $p=.00$). This research matched the premises of Oodith & Parumasur (2015) that it

became the task of the firm's call center to cradle customer interaction and loyalty through ease and speed of access, quality and ease of communication with call center agents. The importance given by Chicu et al. (2016) emphasized the positive human resources practices to increase the performance of call center employees in terms of burnt-out, absenteeism, and attrition was valuable. The importance of attitude on quality customers' experience were also supported by Wasan (2018), Akesson et al. (2014), and Rafaeli et al. (2008). Alcover et al. (2020) found that motivations and commitment among the call center agents were significant and vital. However, the results contradicted the arguments of Agarwal et al. (2013) that attitudes, tangibility and empathy had weak impacts on customer satisfaction.

Product has significant impact on the quality of customers' experience with phone support (Wald test=2.81, $p=.00$; $\chi^2=4231.80$, $p=.00$). Product, as the main deliverable, is the most significant predictor of quality customer experience. Customer experience was commonly measured based on quality of products and services. The results of this research corroborated with Alfa et al. (2021), Bhale and Bedi (2021), Sheth et al. (2020) and Bueno et al. (2019) that products and product quality affect customer experience. Van Dan, Blemer and Henseler (2011) has relevant argument that product information and the suitability of products to customer's situation influences quality customer experience. Again, as customer satisfaction measured the ways companies supply products and services, customer satisfaction also assessed the product use experience compared to the buyer's value expectations (Razak et al. 2019). The conditions pointed by Maklan and Klaus (2011) like the drivers of financial performance, loyalty, satisfaction, and share-of-wallet deserved merit.

First Call Resolution (FCR) has significant impact on the quality of customers' experience with phone support (Wald test=-.64, $p=.00$; $\chi^2=846.59$, $p=.00$). Park et al. (2015) and Sarrab et al. (2016) are correct in claiming that FCR and interpersonal service quality have significant impacts on the overall satisfaction of the customers on the quality of their experience. Govender and Essop (2016) and Labach (2010) converged with this research in including FCR as an element of quality customer experience. Batra (2018) and Sultana (2008) are aligned in arguing that first contact resolution (FCR) affect call center effective performance. In contrast, this research is different from the works of Fernandes (2013) because first call resolution was not related to repurchase behavior.

Quality Customer's Experience has significant impact on the likelihood of repeat purchase with phone support (Wald test=.72, $p=.00$; $\chi^2=1014.38$, $p=.00$). Not all of the antecedents in the SERVQUAL model of Parasuraman (1985) determined quality overall customer experience. Such results did not support the claim of Jaiswal (2008) that service quality management in call centers disregarded customers. The results are contradictory to the results of Park (2020) that interaction quality is the most important dimension of customer experience, because products and outcome quality are the top values of the respondents of this research. Aburayya et al. (2020), Park (2020), Sarrab et al. (2016) and Park et al. (2015) are right in claiming that satisfied customers from product and communication influenced customer experience and then repeat purchase. The arguments of Lestari and Ellyawati (2019) that online service quality (ease of use, website design, security assurance, responsiveness, and personalization) affected customer satisfaction and repurchase intention were validated. Customer interaction and loyalty through ease and speed of access, quality and ease of communication with call center agents were determinants of repeat purchase (Oodith & Parumasu 2015). On the other notes, Bhale and Bedi (2021), Li et al. (2019), Lestari and Ellyawati (2019), Lemon and Verhoef (2016), and Alshurideh et al. (2012) are similar in explaining the positive relationships between quality customer experience and repeat purchase or customer loyalty, while describing possible interventions of personalized approach, different locations, and regular interactions.

Conclusion

To enhance repeat purchase phone support products and services, call center firms need to keep high overall ratings of customers to their experience with phone support by managing product, attitude, wait

time, communication, and first call resolution. Repeat purchase and customer loyalty are results of regular interactions, personalized approach, context of locations, setting values, commitment, training, time allocation and reinforcements. Products and product quality, that highlight clear information, suitability on the customers, and relevant situations, are the most important predictors of quality customers' experience in phone support. Prevention of customers' complaints from happening is a must because majority of customers are not patient with headaches and concerns, a major reason why resolution was not significantly relevant to improve quality customers' experience and repeat purchase. First call resolution indicates chance of recovery of quality customers' experience by relieving pain points at fastest possible time. The quality of products, the perceived caring of the call center agents in the communication and interaction are truly important to keep positive customer experience. The overall customers' experience affects repeat purchase because of the developed confidence over time and the customers' expectations being met.

The COVID-19 pandemic reduces much economic activities and countries such as the Philippines and emerging markets need to rebound (Lim 2020). Call centers are the fastest growing industry in the last decade in the Philippines because of development of satisfied clients (Santos 2020). Call centers created more jobs (Kelibert & Mann 2020). To be strengthened in call center strategies, customer orientation is essential in the trade sector through prompt response to additional and new consumer requests, feedback towards creation of value in all management processes of the distribution network (Valeeva, Bagrova, Gatina & Federova 2020). Throughout Asia in recent decades, automation, digitalization, the Internet, and advanced technologies utterly transform emerging economies, livelihoods, labor markets, and workplaces. Hundreds of millions of laborers were lifted out of poverty as new technology applications created new jobs and industries to drive global integration and prosperity (Mulakala 2019).

Implications for Managers

By enhancing operational excellence, managers are encouraged to promote accurate and reliable products and services. It is further recommended for the call center companies to provide focus on how to communicate caring to customers catered by call centers in their strategies, innovation, and continuous improvement. Reinforcements on caring the customers through programs, recognition, and incentives to call center agents and employees are suggested interventions to keep positive attitude. Moreover, other firms and call center agencies are encouraged to deploy innovative and effective ways to increase repeat purchase by clients from quality customer experience, as guided by the interrelationships between the variables in this study.

For future research, the scale parameters are needed to be specified to check whether non-significant predictors like resolution are significant mediators or moderators. The researchers also suggest future researchers to expand the lists of predictors, such that covariates or continuous predictors are included. The researchers encourage other studies to compare results of customer satisfaction survey of other call centers, products, and services. There is an opportunity to develop a model and equation related to this study. The researchers also encourage the firms and the academia to design human resources practices through human resources management to safeguard the performance of call center employees in truly satisfying their customers (Chicu et al. 2016).

This study has limitations in that it is limited to the regular survey conducted by a single call center firm in the Philippines. The products and services involved are also limited to phone support, network products and routers. The design of this research was limited to non-parametric tests of ordinal data and access to customers a phone support company. However, the use of ordinal logistic regression as a statistical tool is a differentiation from those cited. This study also implied that it was more important and impressive for customers to experience the quality of customer services and relationship, regardless of the resolution or

non-resolution of the issues and concerns about networking and router products, services, and phone support.

References

- Abdullateef AO, Mokhtar, SSM & Yusoff, RZ 2011. The strategic impact of technology-based CRM on call center's performance. *Journal of Internet Banking and Commerce*, 16(1), 2-17.
- Aburayya, A, Marzouqi AA, Alawadhi D, Abdouli F & Taryam M 2020. An empirical investigation of the effect of employees' customer orientation on customer loyalty through the mediating role of customer satisfaction and service quality. *Management Science Letters*, 10, 2147-2158. <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.msl.2020.3.022>
- Agarwal S, Singh D & Thakur KS 2013. Impact of service quality dimensions towards customer satisfaction in Indian Call Centers. *Pacific Business Review International*, 6(1), 51-64. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/341540775>
- Agyapong GKQ 2011. The effect of service quality on customer satisfaction in the utility industry: A case of Vodafone (Ghana). *International Journal of Business Management*, 6(5), 203-210. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijbm.v6n5p203>
- Akesson M, Edvardsson B & Trobvoll B 2014. Customer experience from a self-service system perspective. *Journal of Service Management*, 25 (5), 677-698. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JOSM-01-2013-0016>
- Aksin Z, Ata B, Emadi SM & Su, C-L (2013). Structural estimation of callers' delay sensitivity in call centers. *Management Science*, 1-20. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.2013.1730>
- Alshurideh MT, Nicholson M & Xiao S 2012. The effect of previous experience on mobile subscribers' repeat purchase behavior. *European Journal of Social Sciences*, 30(3), 366-376. <http://www.europeanjournalofsocialsciences.com>
- Alcover CM, Chambel MJ & Estreder Y 2020. Monetary incentives, motivational orientation and affective commitment in contact centers. A multilevel mediation model. *Journal of Economic Psychology*, 81, 1-11 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joep.2020.102307>
- Alfa AA, Addae E, Inkumsah WA & Amponsah RY 2021. Customer experience, social regard, and marketing outcome (satisfaction and loyalty): Sub Saharan oil marketing companies perspective. *Academy of Marketing Studies Journal*, 25 (1), 1-22. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/345859467>
- Ali M & Raza MA 2015. Service quality perception and customer satisfaction in Islamic banks of Pakistan: the modified SERVQUAL model. *Total Quality Management*, 1-18. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/14783363.2015.1100517>
- Baraykar E, Tatoglu E, Turkyilmaz A, Delen D & Zaim S 2012. Measuring the efficiency of customer satisfaction and loyalty for mobile brands with DEA. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 39, 99-106. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2011.06.041>
- Batra MM 2018. Designing a holistic customer experience program. *ResearchGate*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/341606045>
- Bhale UA & Bedi HA 2021. A study on the customer experience of work from home mobile users during COVID 19 pandemic. *Eighteenth AIMS International Conference on Management*, 106-111. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/350440146>
- Bueno EV, Weber TBB, Bomfim EL & Kato HT 2019. Measuring customer experience in service: A systematic review. *The Service Industries Journal*, 1-19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02642069.2018.1561873>
- Charoensukmongko P & Puyod JV 2020. Mindfulness and emotional exhaustion in call center agents in the Philippines: Moderating roles of work and personal characteristics. *The Journal of General Psychology*, 1-25. <https://www.tandfonline.com/loi/vgen20>

- Chicu D, Ryan G & Valverde-Aparicio M 2016. Determinants of customer satisfaction in call centers. *European Accounting and Management Review*, 2(21), 20-41. <https://doi.org/10.26595/eamr.2014.2.2.2>
- Clark CM, Murfett UM, Rogers PS & Ang S 2013. Is empathy effective for customer service? Evidence from call center interactions. *Journal of Business and Technical Communications*, 27(2), 123-153. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1050651912468887>
- Dharamdass S & Fernando Y 2018. Contact service center excellence: a proposed conceptual framework. *International Journal of Services and Operations Management*, 29(1), 18-41. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Yudi_Fernando/publication/322186707_Contact_centre_service_excellence_a_proposed_conceptual_framework/links/5a7857590f7e9b41dbd2a8c8/Contact-centre-service-excellence-a-proposed-conceptual-framework.pdf
- Ellway BPW 2016. Design vs practice: How problematic call routing and rerouting restructures the call center service system. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, 36(4). <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/IJOPM-11-2013-0487>
- Garcia D, Archer T, Moradi S & Ghiabi B 2012. Waiting in vain: Managing time and customer satisfaction at call centers. *Psychology*, 3 (2), 213-216. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4236/psych.2012.32030>
- Giebelhausen MD, Robinson SG & Cronin JJ 2011. Worth waiting for: Increasing satisfaction by making consumers wait. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 39, 889-905. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11747-010-0222-5>
- Govender K & Essop F 2016. Outsourcing in-bound call centers: Impact on customers' service experience. *Journal of Accounting and Marketing*, 5(3), 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.4172/2168-9601.1000187>
- Hair JF, Black WC, Babin BJ & Anderson RE 2010. *Multivariate Data Analysis*. USA, New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
- Hechanova MRM 2013 The call center as a revolving door: A Philippine perspective. *Personnel Review*, 42(3), 349-365. <https://doi.org/10.1108/00483481311320444>
- Jaiswal A 2008. Customer satisfaction and service quality measurement in Indian call centers. *Managing Service Quality*. 18 (4) 405-416. <http://www.atypon-link.com/AMA/doi/abs/10.1509/jmkg.71.2.133>
- Jewitt C & Macley KL 2019. Methodological dialogues across multimodality and sensory ethnography: digital touch communication. *Qualitative Research*, 19(1), 90-110. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1468794118796992>
- Kleibert JM & Mann L 2020. Capturing value amidst constant global restructuring? information-technology-enabled services in India, the Philippines and Kenya. *The European Journal of Development Research*, 32, 1057-1079. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41287-020-00256-1>
- Kumar A 2012. Does the web reduce the customer service cost? Empirical evidence from a Call Center. *Information Systems Research*, 23 (3), 721-737. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1287/isre.1110.0390>
- Labach EJ 2010. Improving customer retention through service quality at call centers. *International Journal of Management and Information Systems-Third Quarter 2010*, 14 (3), 71-76. <https://clutejournals.com/>
- Lemon KN & Verhoef PC 2016. Understanding customer experience throughout the customer journey. *Journal of Marketing*, 80, 69-96. <https://doi.org/10.1509/jm.15.0420>
- Lestari VT & Ellyawati J 2019. Effect of e-service quality on repurchase intention: Testing the role of e-satisfaction as mediator variable. *International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering*, 8 (7C2), 158-162.
- Lew Z, Walthe JB, Pang A & Shin W 2018. Interactivity in online chat: Conversational contingency and response latency in computer-mediated communication. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, 23, 201-221. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jcmc/zmy009>
- Li J & Tsung F 2013. Statistical quality control for the service sector. *Proceedings 59th ISI World Statistics Congress*, 25-30. <http://2013.isiproceedings.org/Files/IPS091-P2-S.pdf>
- Lim JA 2020. The Philippine economy during the COVID Pandemic. *Ateneo Center for Economic Development Working Paper*. 1-28.

- Lu L, Thelen ST & Gregory G 2020. Influence of country of origin and type of information exchanged on consequences of offshore service sentiment. *Journal of Service Theory and Practice*, 30(3), 233-255. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JSTP-02-2019-0045>
- Menaka P & Thangadurai K 2017. Customer satisfaction in SCRM with Key Performance Indicator System. *ICTACT Journal of Management Studies*, 3(2), 515-522. <https://doi.org/10.21917/ijms.2017.0070>
- Li J, Hudson S & So KKF 2019. Exploring the customer experience with Airbnb. *International Journal of Culture, Tourism, and Hospitality Research*, 13(4), 410-429. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCTHR-10-2018-0148>
- Maklan S & Klaus P 2011. Customer experience: Are we measuring the right things? *The Market Research Society*. <https://doi.org/10.2501/IJMR-53-6-771-792>
- Markoulidakis I, Rallis I, Georgoulas I, Kopsiaftis G, Doulamis A & Doulamis N 2020. A machine learning based classification method for customer experience analysis. *Technologies*, 8(76), 1-22. <https://doi.org/10.3390/technologies8040076>
- Mehrotra V, Ross K, Ryder G & Zhou, Y-P 2012. Routing to manage resolution and waiting time in call centers with heterogeneous servers. *Manufacturing and Service Operations Management*, 14(1), 66-81. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1287/msom.1110.0349>
- Morandat C, Nohara H & Tchobanian R 2005. French call center industry report 2004. 16-18. <https://halshs.archives-ouvertes.fr/halshs-00430100/document>
- Mulakala A 2019. The fourth industrial revolution and the future of work: Implications for Asian Development Corporation. *Asian Approaches to Development Cooperation*, 1-237.
- Muswera N, Jordaan BD & Matikiti R 2014. The relationship between employee attributes and customer satisfaction: A case of South African call center industry. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 5(23), 396-405. <https://doi.org/10.5901/mjss.2014.v5n23p396>
- Oodith D 2019. Enhanced customer interactions through customer-centric technology within a call center. *Journal of Economics and Behavioral Studies*, 11(2), 79-91. [https://doi.org/10.22610/jebbs.v11i2\(J.2820](https://doi.org/10.22610/jebbs.v11i2(J.2820)
- Oodith D & Parumasur SB 2015. Call center ease of communication in customer service delivery: An asset to managing customer needs? *Problems and Perspectives in Management*, 13(2), 482-494. <https://www.businessperspectives.org>
- Parasuraman A, Zeithaml VA and Berry LL 1985. A conceptual model of service quality and its implications for future research. *Journal of Marketing*, 49(4), 41-50. <https://doi.org/10.1177/002224298504900403>
- Park JK, Chung T-L, Gunn F & Rutherford B 2015. The role of listening in e-contact center customer relationship management. *Journal of Services Marketing*, 29(1), 49-58. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JSM-02-2014-0063>
- Patmore F & Haddoud M 2015. The drivers and barriers facing Small to Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) entering the US market. *Journal of Research Studies in Business Management*, 1(1), 259-280. <http://www.jrsbm.com/wp-content/uploads/2015/07/JRSBM-Vol-1-Patmore.pdf>
- Rafaeli A, Ziklik, L & Doucet, L 2008. The impact of call center employees' customer orientation on service quality. *Journal of Service Research*, 10(3), 239-255. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1094670507306685>
- Razak MAA & Nayan SM 2020. The price of customer satisfaction. *Journal of Undergraduate Social Science and Technology*, 2(2), 1-5. <https://abm.asia/ojs>
- Rendon CMC, Vasquez A, Benjumea-Arias M & Valencia-Arias A 2017. Proposed model for measuring customer satisfaction with telecommunications services. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 8(2), 15-25. <https://doi.org/10.5901/mjss.2017.v8n2p15>
- Saberi M, Hussain OK & Chang E 2015. Past, present and future of contact centers: A literature review. *Business Process Management Journal*, 23(3), 574-597. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BPMJ-02-2015-0018>

- Santos JC 2020. The relationship of managerial styles to employee job satisfaction in selected business process outsourcing firms in the Philippines. *Journal of Advanced Management Science*, 8(1), 28-32. <https://doi.org/10.18178/joams.8.1.28-32>
- Sarrab M, Elbasir M & Alnaeli S 2016. Towards a quality model of the technical aspects for mobile learning services: an empirical observation. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 55, 100-112. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2015.09.003>
- Sheth J, Jain V & Ambika A 2020. Repositioning the customer support services: The next frontier of competitive advantage. *European Journal of Marketing*, 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EJM-02-2020-0086>
- Sultana N 2008. Achieving customer satisfaction through customer experience management. *CMRD Journal of Management Research*, 59-63.
- Valeeva YS, Bagrova EA, Gatina EA & Federova OV 2020. Advances in Economics, Business and Management Research, 114, 77-82.
- Van Dan, Z, Blemer J & Henseler J 2011. Perceived customer contact center quality: Conceptual foundation and scale development. *The Service Industries Journal*, 31(8), 1347-1363. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02642060903437584>
- Walsh G, Gouthier M, Gremler DD & Brach S 2012. What the eye does not see, the mind cannot reject: Can call center location explain differences in customer evaluations? *International Business Review*, 21, 957-967. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ibusrev.2011.11.002>
- Wasan P 2018. Predicting customer experience and discretionary behaviors of bank customers in India. *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, 36 (4), 701-725. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJBM-06-2017-0121>
- Xia Y, Chen B, Jayaraman B & Munson CL 2015. Competition and market segmentation of the call center service supply chain. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 247, 505-514. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2015.06.027>

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